

Adaptación de cadena de Búsqueda con publish or perish

Fuente de datos	Cadena
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("quantum era" OR "critical infrastructure"))
Springer	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("quantum era" OR "critical infrastructure")
Google Scholar	"cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS" AND "cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model" AND "best practices" OR "cybersecurity frameworks" AND "quantum era" OR "critical infrastructure"

BASES DE DATOS	CANTIDAD	Eliminados (x duplicados)	Incluidos	Excluidos	Relevantes	Primarios
GOOGLE ACADEMICO	256	7	130	122	54	30
SCOPUS	75		0	75	0	0
SPRINGER	89		10	76	10	10